

PRINCIPLES OF LITERARY EDUCATION IN A SPECIAL SCHOOL

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Abstract: This article analyzes the pedagogical principles of organizing literary education classes in special schools, their essence and significance in increasing educational efficiency. Taking into account the age, psychological and individual characteristics of students in the process of literary education, the role of the principles of systematic, consistent, visual, differential and individual approach of education is highlighted. It also reveals the possibilities of literary education in the perception and analysis of works of art, the development of oral and written speech, and the formation of spiritual and moral qualities in students with special educational needs.

Keywords: special school, literary education, educational principles, inclusive education, differentiated education, individual approach, analysis of literary works, systematicity, special pedagogy.

Introduction

Today, in the education system, the issue of providing quality education, taking into account the capabilities, needs, and developmental characteristics of each child, is becoming increasingly relevant. In particular, the acquisition of knowledge, independent thinking, speech activity, and social adaptation of students in special schools are directly linked to the proper organization of the educational process. In this regard, literary education lessons are an important educational tool not only for enriching the knowledge of special school students but also for shaping their spiritual world, developing aesthetic taste, and understanding the environment and human relations.

Literature conveys to the reader's consciousness through artistic images such high qualities as the human heart, life experience, kindness, mercy, patriotism, friendship, and honesty. In the conditions of a special school, the process of working with a literary text requires a deeper pedagogical approach. This is because in such educational institutions, students' cognitive activity, speech development, level of perception, and their ability to remember and analyze may vary. Therefore, in organizing literary education lessons, it is necessary to rely on special pedagogical principles alongside general didactic principles.

In a special school, literary education lessons should not be limited to introducing students to the content of a literary work. Such lessons should activate the student's thinking activity, expand their vocabulary, form their

figurative thinking, and develop skills for understanding and reacting to the content of the text. In particular, the effective use of methods such as assigning tasks to students' capabilities, step-by-step explanation of the topic, use of visual aids, question-and-answer, conversation, role-playing, and expressive reading increases the educational and developmental potential of the lesson.

Adhering to principles in literary education classes is closely linked to the teacher's methodological skills. The principle of systematicity and consistency ensures that educational material is presented in a logical sequence, while the principle of visualization helps to bring artistic images and events to life in the reader's imagination. The principles of an individual and differentiated approach serve to provide education that corresponds to the capabilities, interests, and level of development of each student. Furthermore, the principle of consciousness and activity transforms the student into an active participant in the lesson process, shaping their skills in expressing opinions, asking questions, and drawing conclusions.

Another important aspect of literary education in special schools is that it has a strong impact on the socialization of students. Through the life events, characters, and their actions and experiences depicted in literary works, students understand human relationships and learn to distinguish between good and bad behavior. This is of great importance in shaping their moral views, emotional sensitivity, and attitude toward life. Especially for students with special educational needs, the literature lesson serves as a school for engaging in communication, expressing one's thoughts, and understanding others.

Therefore, one of the important tasks facing today's special pedagogy is the scientific and pedagogical study of the principles of literary education in a special school and the determination of ways to implement them in practice. This article highlights the core principles of effective literary education classes in special schools, their role in developing the student's personality, and their methodological significance.

Theoretical basis

The issue of organizing literary education classes in a special school is inextricably linked to the disciplines of general pedagogy, special pedagogy, psychology, literary studies, and methodology. This is because the process of literary education involves not only conveying the content of a work of art to the student but also ensuring their personal development, speech activity, aesthetic taste, moral views, and social adaptation. In this regard, the principles of literary education in special schools are determined in accordance with the capabilities,

cognitive processes, psychophysiological characteristics and individual needs of students.

In the theoretical basis of literary education, first of all, the humanitarian principle of education occupies an important place. According to this principle, every student is considered an individual with unique developmental potential. When working with students of special schools, it is necessary to rely not on their existing shortcomings, but on the opportunities that can be developed. Literature lessons have a great educational and developmental power in this regard. Through literary works, the reader becomes acquainted with human feelings, life events, the characters, and social relations. This process serves to develop the student's emotional perception, thinking, and speech skills.

From the point of view of special pedagogy, literary education should have a correctional-developmental character. That is, during the lesson, it is intended not only for the student to acquire knowledge but also to reduce their speech, cognitive, emotional, and communicative difficulties. For example, activities such as listening to a literary text, reading, retelling, characterizing characters, and finding answers to questions develop students' skills in hearing, seeing, remembering, understanding, thinking, and communicating. Therefore, literary education is considered not as a simple subject in a special school, but as a pedagogical process that comprehensively develops the personality.

One of the important theoretical foundations of literary education classes is the principle of systematic and consistent education. In the conditions of a special school, the educational material should be presented step by step according to the level of complexity, first easy concepts, and then relatively complex artistic images and ideas should be explained. The reader may not be able to deeply analyze the literary text at once. Therefore, when working with the text, first its theme, sequence of events, characters, then the main idea and educational content are revealed. Such an approach helps the student gradually acquire knowledge, consciously assimilate concepts, and draw independent conclusions.

The principle of visualization is also one of the main criteria ensuring the effectiveness of literary education in a special school. It is important to use pictures, objects, stage scenes, audio recordings, video clips, facial expressions, and movements to bring the events, images, and images of works of art to life in the reader's mind. Especially for students who face difficulties in the process of perception and imagination, visual aids make it easier to understand the content of the text. Visuality concretizes the artistic image, interests the student in the lesson, and strengthens their emotional attitude.

From a theoretical standpoint, the principles of the individual and differential approach are considered the central foundations of specialized school literary education. The level of speech development, memory, attention stability, reading speed, and text comprehension capabilities of each student are not the same. Therefore, the teacher must adapt the tasks to the individual capabilities of the students. Some students are comfortable listening to the text and answering based on the picture, while others can read the short text independently and tell the content. Consequently, applying tasks of various levels during the lesson process, rather than being limited to a single requirement, increases educational efficiency.

Another theoretical basis of literary education is the principle of consciousness and activity. The reader should not accept the work of art as ready-made information, but should be encouraged to understand it, ask questions, express opinions and express their attitude. Methods such as conversation, question-and-answer, role-playing, dramatization, storytelling based on pictures, and character evaluation are effective for forming activity in special school students. These methods enhance the student's participation in the lesson and develop independent thinking and communication culture.

The principle of upbringing is of particular importance in literary education classes. Literary works serve to form in students such qualities as kindness, mercy, patriotism, diligence, honesty, friendship, and humanism. For special school students, this process is even more important, as they understand real-life relationships through artistic images and learn to respond to their own behavior by evaluating the characters' behavior. In this sense, literature lessons serve as an effective means of moral education, emotional development, and social adaptation.

The principles of literary education in a special school are also related to the communicative approach. A literature lesson must create an environment that engages students in communication and develops their oral and written speech. Talking about a literary text, speaking on behalf of the characters, retelling the story, and expressing one's thoughts in simple sentences forms the speech competence of students. Especially for children with special educational needs, the development of speech activity is an important factor in their adaptation to social life.

Also, the theoretical basis of literary education is the issue of aesthetic education. A work of art teaches the reader to feel beauty, to think figuratively, to understand the power of the word. If aesthetic education in a special school is

carried out not through simple explanation, but through means such as emotional perception, expressive reading, music, drawing, and staging, its impact will increase. This develops the student's imagination, sensitivity, and creative activity.

Discussion

The effective organization of literary education lessons in a special school is determined, first and foremost, by the correct selection and practical application of pedagogical principles used during the lesson process. In such educational institutions, literature lessons should be viewed not as a simple academic subject, but as an important pedagogical process that influences the speech, emotional, mental, moral, and social development of the student. This is because special school students have different abilities for perception, memorization, thinking, understanding text content, and expressing their thoughts. Therefore, it is important to take into account the individual characteristics of each student in literary education classes, to organize the content of the lesson in a simple, understandable, step-by-step and visual form.

During the discussion, it should be emphasized that the main task of literary education in special schools is not only to teach the content of a work of art. The literature lesson enriches the student's life experience, expands their vocabulary, develops their communication skills, and helps them understand social relations. For example, through a fairy tale, story, poem, or fable, the reader figuratively perceives concepts such as good and evil, friendship and betrayal, diligence and laziness, kindness and indifference. This serves to form the student's skills in moral assessment, expression of attitude, and drawing conclusions.

The effectiveness of literary education lessons in a special school largely depends on the correctional-developmental principle. This principle is aimed at eliminating or reducing students' existing difficulties during the lesson process and developing their preserved potential. In the process of working on a literary text, students listen to the text, read it, answer questions, recount events sequentially, describe the characters, and express their attitude. Each of these activities serves to develop speech, memory, attention, thinking, and imagination. Consequently, the literary education lesson manifests as a natural and effective form of correctional work in a special school.

It is also important to adhere to the principles of systematicity and consistency during the lesson. For special school students, if literary material is presented in the form of a complex analysis all at once, it becomes difficult for them to fully grasp the content of the text. Therefore, when studying a work of art,

the teacher must first determine the theme of the text, then explain the sequence of main events, reveal the characters, and then discuss the ideological and educational content of the work. Such a step-by-step approach helps students more easily perceive and firmly master the lesson content.

The principle of visualization is of particular importance in the context of a special school. Events and characters depicted in literary works can often be abstract for the reader. Therefore, the use of pictures, objects, audio and video materials, stage performances, facial expressions, gestures, and dramatization methods helps to understand the content of the text more accurately. For example, showing the picture of the characters in the fairy tale, arranging the sequence of events through images, or performing actions corresponding to the content of the poem activates the reader's perception. As a result, the literary text becomes not only audible or readable information for the reader, but also a life reality that can be seen, felt and understood.

Applying the principles of an individual and differentiated approach is one of the most important conditions for literary education in a special school. This is because the level of preparation, speech development, reading skills, and independent thinking capabilities of students in the same class are not the same. Therefore, the teacher should not limit themselves to giving the same assignment to all students. Some students may be given tasks such as answering based on a picture, others composing short sentences, and still others retelling the text or evaluating a character's behavior. Such an approach ensures the development of students in accordance with their capabilities and creates conditions for active participation in the lesson.

A special place in the topic under discussion is occupied by the teacher's methodological skills. A teacher conducting a literary education lesson in a special school should not be limited to knowing only the content of literature, but also deeply master the basics of special pedagogy, psychology, speech development methodology, and correctional education. The teacher must listen to the student's answer patiently, direct them correctly without sharp criticism of their mistakes, and instill confidence in them through encouragement. This is because the interest and activity of students with special educational needs in the lesson largely depend on the teacher's attitude, support, and the positive psychological atmosphere in the lesson.

The issue of developing a student's speech in literary education classes is also one of the important areas of discussion. Working with a literary text increases the student's vocabulary, forms sentence formation skills, and develops oral and

written expression. In particular, exercises such as conducting a question-and-answer session based on the text, explaining new words, describing characters, narrating a short story, and expressing one's opinion increase students' speech activity. For special school students, speech development is crucial for their socialization, self-expression, and communication with others.

The practical significance of the educational principle in literary education classes is also very great. Literary works influence the minds of students not through direct advice, but through images, events, and the fates of characters. This method is especially effective for special school students, as they more easily grasp moral concepts through specific events and images. For example, the fact that an honest hero is rewarded, or that a liar or lazy hero faces difficulties, allows students to draw a moral conclusion. Thus, the literature lesson serves as an important tool in shaping the student's moral views and social behavior. It is also important to organize literary education classes in a special school based on modern pedagogical technologies. The use of interactive methods, role-playing games, group work, dramatization, clusters, storytelling based on pictures, question cards, and audio and multimedia tools increases students' interest in the lesson. However, the capabilities of students must be taken into account when applying such technologies. Any method yields effective results only when it corresponds to the lesson goal, the student's level of development, and the content of the literary text.

As a result of the discussion, it can be concluded that the educational process will be effective when the principles of literary education are applied interconnectedly in a special school. The principles of humanism, correctional-developmental, demonstrative, systematic, individual and differential approach, consciousness-activity, and educational principles complement each other. Although each of them is of particular importance, in practice, they manifest as a unified pedagogical system.

In conclusion, strict adherence to pedagogical principles in organizing literary education classes in special schools serves to develop students' understanding of the literary text, speech activity, thinking ability, aesthetic taste, and spiritual and moral qualities. A literature lesson is a powerful educational tool that influences the student's heart, encouraging them to think, feel, communicate, and understand life. Therefore, literary education lessons in a special school should be organized in accordance with the capabilities and needs of each student, based on kindness, patience, demonstration and consistency.

List of references

1. Tolipov U., Usmonboyeva M. Applied foundations of pedagogical technologies. – Tashkent: Fan, 2017. – 262 p.
2. Hasanboyeva O., Turakulov Kh., Khaidarov M. et al. Pedagogy. – Tashkent: Science and Technology, 2020. – 512 p.
3. Kadyrov B.R. General Pedagogy. - Tashkent: Tafakkur Bustoni, 2019. – 320 p.
4. Pulatova P.M. Special Pedagogy. – Tashkent: Science and Technology, 2021. - 368 p.
5. Nurkeldiyeva D.A. Fundamentals of Special Pedagogy. – Tashkent: O'qituvchi, 2020. – 284 p.
6. Zunnunov A., Eshonkulov J. Methodology of Teaching Literature. - Tashkent: O'qituvchi, 2019. – 240 p.
7. Yuldashev K. Scientific and theoretical foundations of teaching literature. – Tashkent: New Century Generation, 2020. – 288 p.

